

Complexes of Nickel-, Zinc-, Palladium- and Cadmium(II) with some Furan-2-thiohydrazones

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The complexes of a number of metal ions with furan-2-thiohydrazone and other substituted thiohydrazone have been reported^{1,2}. We report here the preparation of complexes of furan-2-thiohydrazones (A and B) with acetone (act.ftH), furfural (fftH) and salicylaldehyde (sal.ftH₂).

R = 2-furan or *o*-phenol

Results and Discussion

The complexes (Table 1) in general are insoluble in water but dissolve appreciably in DMF. Bis-ligated complexes as well as [M(sal.ft)py] are soluble in methanol, ethanol and dioxane, but [M(sal.ft)], (M = Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} or Pd^{II}) and [Ni(sal.ft).H₂O] are almost insoluble in methanol and ethanol. The insolubility of [M(sal.ft)] type of complexes indicates their dimeric or polymeric nature. Except [Ni(sal.ft).H₂O] which is feebly paramagnetic ($\mu_{\text{eff}} = 0.62$ B.M.), the other complexes are diamagnetic. The diamagnetism of the Ni^{II} and Pd^{II} complexes indicates their square-planar structure³. A minor paramagnetism of [Ni(sal.ft).H₂O] can be attributed to partial population of a spin-triplet state close to idealised ground state ¹A_{1g} for D_{4h} symmetry⁴. The preference for tetrahedral stereochemistry for complexes of d¹⁰ electronic system and observed metal ligand stoichiometry⁵ indicate tetrahedral structure for the Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes.

The solid reflectance spectra of the Ni^{II} and Pd^{II} complexes display spectral pattern similar to square-planar geometry⁶. A medium band or shoulder in the spectra of the Ni^{II} complexes at 460–490 nm is assigned to ¹A_{1g} → ¹B_{1g} transition in planar field. A strong absorption below 400 nm is attributed to charge transfer transition. A shoulder or medium band at 410–440 nm observed for the Pd^{II} complexes is attributed to ¹A_{1g} → ¹A_{1g} transition in square-planar field⁷.

The ir spectra of [ML₂], (M = Ni^{II}, Pd^{II}, Zn^{II} or Cd^{II}; LH = act.ftH.fftH), [M(sal.ft)py] and [M(sal.ft).nH₂O] (M = Ni^{II}, Pd^{II}, Zn^{II} or Cd^{II}; n = 0 or 1) do not display NH stretch indicating that ligands are deprotonated in the complexes. A broad band at 2950–3150 cm⁻¹ for [M(sal.ftH₂)₂]

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd./ (Colour)	Analysis% : Found/(Calcd.)		Λ_{m} $\Omega^{-1}\text{cm}^2\text{mol}^{-1}$
	M	N	
Ni(act.ft) ₂ (Brown)	13.83 (14.01)	13.45 (13.30)	3
Pd(act.ft) ₂ (Orange)	22.67 (22.15)	11.66 (11.69)	5
Zn(act.ft) ₂ (Yellow)	15.68 (15.32)	13.07 (13.10)	7
Cd(act.ft) ₂ (Yellow)	22.96 (23.63)	11.45 (11.81)	5
Ni(fft) ₂ (Brown)	11.86 (11.87)	10.82 (11.26)	4
Pd(fft) ₂ (Red)	19.16 (19.48)	10.43 (10.29)	5
Zn(fft) ₂ (Yellow)	12.68 (13.01)	10.91 (11.22)	6
Cd(fft) ₂ (Yellow)	20.11 (20.36)	9.78 (10.18)	4
Ni(sal.ftH) ₂ (Brown)	10.50 (10.75)	9.90 (10.20)	8
Pd(sal.ftH) ₂ (Brown)	17.42 (17.78)	9.21 (9.39)	10
Zn(sal.ftH) ₂ (Yellow)	11.61 (11.79)	9.76 (10.08)	9
Cd(sal.ftH) ₂ (Yellow)	18.40 (18.60)	9.18 (9.30)	8
Ni(sal.ft).H ₂ O (Brown)	18.11 (18.32)	8.67 (8.72)	3
Zn(sal.ft) (Yellow)	20.50 (21.16)	9.08 (9.05)	4
Cd(sal.ft) (Yellow)	29.41 (31.46)	6.26 (7.86)	3
Pd(sal.ft) (Yellow)	29.81 (30.28)	7.89 (8.00)	4
Ni(sal.ft)py (Red)	15.21 (14.50)	10.91 (10.32)	5
Pd(sal.ft)py (Yellow)	24.81 (23.85)	9.90 (9.25)	6
Zn(sal.ft)py (Yellow)	16.60 (15.84)	10.81 (10.57)	3
Cd(sal.ft)py (Yellow)	26.51 (24.35)	9.67 (9.14)	3

(M = Zn^{II}, Ni^{II}, Pd^{II} or Cd^{II}) which is absent in [M(sal.ft).H₂O] and [M(sal.ft)], indicates that phenolic OH

of salicylaldehyde part is retained in bis-chelates and involved in hydrogen bonding while deprotonated and coordinated to metal in monoligated complexes. The hydrated complexes $[\text{Ni}(\text{sal.ft})\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ display a broad band near 3350 cm^{-1} attributed to water molecule. The rocking band of H_2O is not observed for coordinated water which indicates lattice nature of H_2O in the complexes⁹.

The $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ band of azomethene group of the ligands ($1625 \pm 5\text{ cm}^{-1}$) is observed at $1605 \pm 10\text{ cm}^{-1}$ as strong band in the complexes¹⁰. The thioamide bands I, II and III of the complexes are observed at $1560\text{--}1500$, $1390\text{--}1320$, $1295\text{--}1230\text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively¹¹. The thioamide band IV of the free ligands ($865\text{--}935\text{ cm}^{-1}$) which has major contribution from $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ vibration is observed at $705 \pm 20\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in their complexes, indicating that thioamide sulphur is involved in bonding on deprotonation of thiol sulphur^{11,12}. Thus from ir spectral pattern it is inferred that deprotonated thiol sulphur and azomethene nitrogen are bonding sites of all the ligand molecules^{10,11}.

In case of monoligated complexes $[\text{M}(\text{sal.ft})]$, ($\text{M} = \text{Zn}^{\text{II}}$, Cd^{II} , Ni^{II}), $[\text{Ni}(\text{sal.ft})\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ and $[\text{M}(\text{sal.ft})\text{py}]$, the fact that $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ is observed at $1280\text{--}1330\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and which is observed at lower frequencies ($1180\text{--}1250\text{ cm}^{-1}$) for bis-chelates and free ligand, indicates that phenolic oxygen is bonded to metal atom probably as bridging atom in monoligated complexes¹⁰. The pyridine ring $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ band is observed at $1595 \pm 5\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes. The pyridine ring breathing mode of vibration observed at $1020 \pm 5\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is regarded as coordinated nature of pyridine molecule¹¹. The pyridino complexes display its characteristic vibration at 665 , 584 ± 3 and $525 \pm 4\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for coordinated pyridine molecule¹². In far-ir region, the bands at 466 ± 8 , 365 ± 15 and $333 \pm 12\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are tentatively attributed to a $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$, $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M-S}}$ vibrations¹³.

Experimental

Furan-2-thiohydrazide (ftH) was prepared by reported method¹⁴. Furan-2-thiohydrazones were prepared by condensing appropriate aldehyde or ketone in hot methanol and crystallising from hot benzene.

$[\text{M}(\text{LH})_2]$, ($\text{M} = \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}$, Pd^{II} , Zn^{II} or Cd^{II} , $\text{LH} = \text{act.ftH}$, fftH or sal.ftH_2): An aqueous solution (30–40 ml) of the metal chloride (0.001 mol) was added slowly with stirring to a hot ethanolic solution (40–50 ml) of appropriate ligand (0.002 mol) when the metal complexes separated immediately. The solid products were digested on a steam-bath, washed with aqueous ethanol, dried over CaCl_2 and finally in an air oven at $60\text{--}70^\circ$.

$[\text{M}(\text{sal.ft})]\cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$, ($\text{M} = \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}$, Pd^{II} , Zn^{II} or Cd^{II} ; $n=1$ or 0): An aqueous solution (40–50 ml) of the appropriate

metal acetate (0.001 mol) and the chloride in case of Pd^{II} , containing 10% aqueous solution (20 ml) of sodium acetate was treated with a hot ethanolic solution of the ligand. The solid products were digested on a steam-bath for 0.5 h, washed with ethanol and dried as above.

$[\text{M}(\text{sal.ft})\text{Py}]$, ($\text{M} = \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}$, Pd^{II} , Zn^{II} or Cd^{II}): An aqueous solution (50 ml) of the metal chloride (0.001 mol) was treated with pyridine (3–4 ml) and the resulting pyridino complexes were refluxed with molar ratio of ethanol solution of the ligand for 0.5 h, when mixed ligand complexes separated out. The solid products were washed with aqueous ethanol and dried over $\text{KOH} + \text{CaCl}_2$.

The physical data of the complexes were obtained as reported earlier¹.

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